

Revitalizing Basque informal address form *hika*: Current discussions regarding gender

Beñat Muguruza¹, Garbiñe Bereziartua²

Abstract

The Basque language is considered a gender-neutral language because it does not show grammatical gender. Nonetheless, Basque has some traits in which gender-markers are present. The most prominent could be the informal form of address, *hika* (derived from the singular second-person personal pronoun “hi”), in which the addressee’s gender needs to be marked in the verb. However, the use of *hika* is quite limited these days, especially the forms used to address women. Most Basque speakers only use the formal and gender-neutral address term, *zuka*. In recent years, however, we are witnessing efforts to revitalize *hika*, with a clear focus on its female forms. *Hika* is reclaimed among women associated with positive values, such as (self-)confidence and sisterhood. At the same time, the use of *hika* poses two issues. First, it is based on a gender binary system, which may not respond to current gender diversity in society. Second, there is a tendency of a sexist use of *hika* through the preference for male forms. Meanwhile, the address form *zuka* does not present either of these challenges. Speakers may face a dilemma: they are struggling to recover an address form that can discriminate against some speakers, while there is already a gender-neutral address form that is used by most Basque speakers. To explore actual speakers’ disposition about *hika* and the gender issues its use has implicated, we organized six focus group discussions with 24 people of different profiles who have daily contact with *hika*. In addition, we also conducted seven dyadic interviews with more qualified participants. Most of the participants do not identify *hika* as a potential threat for gender-inclusive language. They think making an effort to revitalize the informal address form —especially among women— is worthwhile.

Keywords

Forms of address, gender, gender inclusive language, Basque language, *hika*

¹ University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), Spain, E-mail: benat.muguruza@ehu.eus,
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8095-1927>

² University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), Spain, E-mail: garbine.bereziartua@ehu.eus,
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4987-3315>

Introduction

The Basque language or *euskara* is a minoritized language spoken on both sides of the western Pyrenees. The Basque language has undergone a constant decline over the centuries, but the most restrictive era was during Franco's dictatorship (1939–1975) on the Spanish side of the Basque Country (Gondra, 2024). Once democracy was reinstated, it was made official together with Spanish in the Basque Autonomous Community (BAC), the most populous region in the whole area. The newly created Basque government established a very progressive language policy, following the work of grassroots movements in favor of the Basque language that had begun clandestinely during the final years of the dictatorship.

The education system has been one of the most important elements of the Basque revitalization process (Garcia-Ruiz et al., 2024). In the 2024–25 academic year, 70% of students in the BAC are enrolled in Basque immersion programs. This figure represents students ranging from two-year-old children to vocational training students, while the percentage is much higher in preschool and primary education.

According to the latest sociolinguistic survey, 809,341 people over the age of 16 can speak Basque and a further 431,092 have only passive knowledge of the language (Basque Government et al., 2024). That is, 30.2% of the population can use Basque actively and a further 16.1% are able to understand it. Significantly enough, 50% of young Basque speakers (age 16–24) had a language other than Basque at home and learned Basque at school. Most of them only speak the standard variety *Euskara batua* ('unified Basque'), which was created in 1968 and is nowadays used in education, public administration, the mass media, and literature (see Gondra, 2024).

The Basque informal address form *hika*: an exception in a grammatically gender-neutral language

A couple of observations should be made at the outset for those who are not familiar with the Basque language. It is a language isolate genetically unrelated to any other. In the words of Trask (1997: 35), Basque is "the sole surviving pre-Indo-European language of western Europe". Furthermore, it is considered a gender-neutral language because there is no grammatical gender in the nominal system; that is nouns and adjectives have no distinct endings depending on gender (Laka, 1996). However, there is a domain in which gender differences are present: a specific address form, which we proceed to explain as follows.

The address form system of the Basque language is rather complex (see Alberdi, 2018). Basque has a total of four address forms, albeit with a very uneven distribution throughout the Basque-speaking area. Apart from *zuka* and *hika*, which are currently the most used address forms, the other two forms are the virtually extinct *berorika*, stemming from the pronominal form *berori*, a trait of "hyper-politeness" or "deference," "used to address priests and very prominent persons" (Alberdi, 2018: 307); and the address form the address

form *xuka* is employed in certain areas of the northern Basque Country and should be placed somewhere in between *zuka* and *hika* regarding the level of formality. The present study takes into consideration the two main address forms: *zuka* (V) and *hika* (T). They both stem from the speaker’s choice of second-person personal pronoun. If interlocutors choose the formal pronoun *zu*, then they will speak in *zuka*, whereas the choice of the informal pronoun *hi* will entail using *hika*. In the latter case, verbal morphology is directly affected. When *hi* takes an object, or when the addressee is the indirect object, the addressee’s gender is encoded in the verb. Even if the addressee is not an argument of the verb, the speaker needs to add a morpheme referring to the interlocutor if they are using *hi*, which will vary with the addressee’s gender. This rare characteristic is called allocutivity. Allocutivity has been observed in some other languages but the Basque case has received most academic attention (see Antonov, 2015; Haddican, 2018; Oyharçabal, 1993).

Thus, if we are using *zuka* as in example (1) below, no gender marker is present. In examples (2) and (3), we observe the use of the informal address form, *hika*, and they display gender differences marked in the verb, depending on the addressee’s (assumed) gender³. Sentences (4) – (6) are examples with first-person singular subjects. The verb in example (4) is not affected because the formal address form is being employed, but in examples (5) and (6) the speaker is using *hika*, so they are required to encode the addressee’s gender within the verb even though there is no reference to the addressee in the sentence. Female forms of *hika* are called *noka* and male forms are called *toka*, and these terms will be used throughout the study.

- (1) **Zuk** mendia ikusten **duzu**. [You see the mountain. (*Zuka*, neutral)]
- (2) **Hik** mendia ikusten **dun**. [You see the mountain. (*Hika*, female addressee)]
- (3) **Hik** mendia ikusten **duk**. [You see the mountain. (*Hika*, male addressee)]
- (4) **Nik** mendia ikusten **dut**. [I see the mountain. (*Zuka*, neutral)]
- (5) **Nik** mendia ikusten **dinat**. [I see the mountain. (*Hika*, female addressee, allocutive)]
- (6) **Nik** mendia ikusten **diat**. [I see the mountain. (*Hika*, male addressee, allocutive)]

According to the most widely accepted hypothesis, *hi* used to be the only singular second-person personal pronoun (*zu* being the plural pronoun) until the Middle Ages but, for various reasons, *zu* became singular and a new second-person plural pronoun was created (*zuek*). Thus, *hi* started competing with the more formal *zu* and, contrary to the trends in the Romance languages geographically surrounding the Basque language, the informal address form *hika* has lost ground in favor of *zuka* (Alberdi, 1996). In fact, these days *zuka* can be regarded as “the pragmatically unmarked form of address” (Echeverria, 2003: 397).

Even in the areas where *hika* is still used, certain conditions should be met so that speakers engage in a conversation using the informal personal pronoun *hi*. Although “generalizations about *hika* are more difficult to make” (Echeverria, 2020:11), Alberdi (1996) suggests some strategies of use in which different factors come into play. They can include the closer the kinship, the easier speakers will use *hika*. Additionally, bigger age difference may trigger an asymmetric use of address forms, i.e., a father may address his son using *hi*, but the opposite is rare. The gender factor is crucial in all types of relationships: men use *hika* more often and mainly to address other men. Alberdi (2018: 315) more recently

³ Some *hika* forms that agree with a second-person argument are gender-neutral, too (see Alberdi, 2018).

discusses his findings from the early 90s and observes that “it is reasonable to think that address forms and usage patterns of address might have undergone changes since then.” In fact, research carried out in recent years shows how things have evolved within a relatively short period of time. The use of *hika* in general has waned, but this decline has been unequal in terms of gender.

Different methodologies have been employed to measure the actual use of address forms. Most studies rely on the participants’ reported use of *hika*, and most of them focus on specific towns in which the presence of the informal address form is still high (Azkue, 2000; Aztiker, 2021; Bereziartua & Muguruza, 2021). Alberdi’s (1996) research is based on 210 respondents from 51 towns across the Basque Country in order to get a general picture of the use of the informal address form. Apart from research based on reported use, a few studies have looked at the actual use of *hika* in public via direct observation (Soziolinguistika Klusterra, 2016, 2017, 2022). Whatever the methodology, all findings point in the same direction: the address form *hika* is in the process of becoming a genderlect (see Bereziartua & Muguruza, 2024). That is, while it was commonly used in different contexts by most people who are now roughly over 65, now it is almost exclusively used by and toward men of younger generations; more often in friendship contexts than in the family environment. In fact, even if Echeverria (2020: 11) states that “the bastion of *hi* remains the family,” recent data reveal that the family has ceased to be the stronghold of *hika* and most boys acquire it mainly by listening to older boys at school. In any case, this phenomenon only takes place massively in areas where *hika* is very present. This relationship between men (and masculinity) and *hika* is not new but the association seems to be stronger than ever in the Basque imaginary (see Echeverria, 2001, 2003; Bereziartua & Muguruza, 2024).

Methodology

We use two datasets in this study. First, we organized six focus group discussions and seven dyadic interviews in which 38 people took part. All the participants were either born or lived in Azpeitia, a town with a population of some 15,000 inhabitants. We needed informants that had close contact with *hika* so that they could relate situations or feelings linked to the use of the Basque informal address form, and Azpeitia is considered a stronghold of *hika* (Bereziartua & Muguruza, 2021). For the focus groups, we recruited participants of different ages (ranging from 14 to 74), gender, academic background, professional activity, and so on. In addition, the seven dyadic interviews allowed us to elicit meaningful data about a phenomenon for which it is not easy to recruit a high number of informants (see Lobe and Morgan, 2021). These interviews consisted of two conductors and two participants. These participants were considered particularly interesting due to their professional relationship with the Basque language and their ability to deeply reflect upon complex issues like the present topic. Both research instruments add up to a recording lasting 20 hours and 27 minutes and produced by 38 informants. The verbatim transcription of all the material consists of 158,199 words. As for the data analysis, the qualitative content analysis method has been used for systematically describing the meaning of qualitative data by assigning successive parts of the material to the categories

of a coding frame (Schreier, 2014). The discussions and the interviews were naturally carried out in Basque, and the authors’ translations of the excerpts into English is provided in the results. We anonymized the participants by displaying the following information in the code: MAN or WOMAN and the age of the participant. Thus, the code WOMAN-26, for example, should be interpreted as follows: a 26-year-old female participant.

Second, we show a set of meaningful examples that we have collected after years of observation. This is material that we have identified in social networks, in the media,⁴ or that we have received from others. This compilation consists of mostly branding examples in very diverse domains: associations, cultural programs, and so on. Other examples are displayed, such as the script of a theater play. All of them are translated into English as accurately as possible.

Contemporary tendencies regarding gender and *hika*

Now we go on to examine some recent phenomena related to these forms that may be considered representative of the complexities of the Basque address system, with a specific focus on gender issues informing the use of *hika*. We cover four different but interrelated phenomena. First, we look at gender-fair language and Basque, and more specifically, how it affects the informal address form *hika*. Second, linked to gender-fair language, some incorrect uses of *hika* are shown. We then explain how the gender binary character of the informal address form *hika* may cause result in some concerns of inclusivity these days. Finally, we show how the pragmatic meanings of female forms of *hika* —also known as *noka*— are evolving of late.

Gender-fair language and *hika*

In recent years, we have witnessed various attempts to make languages more gender-fair. However, depending on the features of each language, the strategies to achieve this goal may differ. Spanish and French are of significance for our study since they are the majority languages of the southern and northern Basque Country, respectively.

Spanish has a binary grammatical gender system, which includes masculine and feminine. Bonnin and Coronel (2021: 2) state that “the gender of nouns agrees with determinants and adjectives, so gender is a very pervasive feature” in the Spanish language. In recent times, different alternatives have been suggested that challenge the so-called inclusive or generic masculine *Spanish pronoun* (see Mendivil, 2020). The use of the symbol @ in writing would represent both women and men, but many consider that in the end it remains binary (Bonnin & Coronel, 2021) and that there is no actual way to pronounce this symbol, hence its impossibility to use in oral language (Velázquez, 2021). The use of the gender-neutral morpheme *-x* has become quite widespread, but it is not applicable for spoken language either (Bonnin & Coronel, 2021; Velázquez, 2021). Another proposal that

⁴ Many of them were published by the *hika* expert Ritxi Lizartza on the website Zuzeu (<https://zuzeu.eus/euskara/hitanoa/>)

has gained momentum recently is the alternative use of the vowel *-e* to create pronouns, nouns, and adjectives (Velázquez, 2021: 41). Interestingly, the innovative introduction of morpheme *-e* can be interpreted differently: it has a gender-neutral value, but it can also acquire a non-binary value depending on the context (Fábregas, 2022). The use of such gender-inclusive markers has increased in recent years, but it seems to be limited to a few specific contexts, such as college campuses and academic settings (Bonnin & Coronel, 2021: 2). Nonetheless, this phenomenon has generated an ongoing and heated debate that is taking place in different spheres (Fábregas, 2022). Bonnin & Coronel (2021) claim that little research has been done on Spanish gender-inclusive language in general, especially on speakers' attitudes and the actual use of such linguistic forms.

In the case of French, although the eminent lexicographer Alain Robert regarded gender-fair language issues as “a storm in a teacup” it seems to be a debate that will persist for some time (Schnitzer, 2021). Different strategies have been suggested of late, such as eliminating the masculine neutral forms in favor of the proximity agreement (‘les mères et les pères impliqués’ or ‘des syndicats et des associations désireuses’), introducing new articles and pronouns, and so on (Della Sudda & Paoletti, 2022: 149). Swamy and Mackenzie (2022), from a mostly non-binary and LGBTQ+ perspective, include so-called neo-pronouns like *iel*, *al*, *ul*, and *ille*, some of which are totally integrated in their writing.

The case of Swedish is unique in several ways so it is worth explaining briefly. The gender-neutral third-person singular pronoun “hen” was first used in a children’s book in 2012 (Sczesny et al., 2016). It was actively created in order to challenge the binary notion of gender (Lindqvist et al., 2018). There have been many attempts in other languages, but the Swedish pronoun “hen” appears to be especially successful. According to Gustaffson et al. (2015: 2), “no other language has so far added a third gender-neutral pronoun that actually has reached the broader population of language users.” As a matter of fact, the Swedish Academy Glossary (SAOL) eventually included this neologism (Lindqvist et al., 2019), which is exceptional in most European contexts.

English has also adopted different strategies to cover the gap of what Saguy and Williams (2022) label as the “missing pronoun,” referring to contexts in which the personal pronoun should not be either “she” or “he” for various reasons. The singular “they” is the most widely used resource, and it is subject to different interpretations (see Saguy & Williams, 2022). Among many other recently made-up pronouns, *ze* has also stood out, but most English speakers do not seem to be familiar with it, and it usually refers only to non-binary gender people (Lindqvist et al., 2019: 114).

As for Basque, it is often considered gender-neutral because it has neither grammatical gender nor natural gender; indeed, it has very few gender traits overall. It is the informal form of address in which we can openly find these gender marks. That said, some authors have questioned whether Basque actually is a grammatically non-sexist language. Barquín (2008) and Juanena (1991), among others, have warned that several factors need to be taken into account before making a categorical claim, such as the mere existence of some words or expressions, or the abundance or scarcity of a given semantic field. Consequently, rather than locating gender within the (grammar of the) language per se, the key to the factors could lie in language use.

Regarding the gender markers of the Basque informal form of address, Barquín (2008) recommends different options varying with the context: (1) using the pronoun *zu* is always an option; (2) the imperative form in Basque allows eliding the auxiliary verb, which can be useful in signs that address the whole population in *hika*; (3) the combined *hika* marker *-nk* can be used, by combining the female morpheme *-n* and the male morpheme *-k*. The veteran cartoonist Antton Olariaga made up this alternative *hika* form in the long-running comic strip called *Zakilixut*, in which the neutral *hika* forms have been employed for about 20 years. His proposal has made some impact in recent years in different cultural settings. Some examples include the well-known TV comedy show *Wazemank* (‘Let’s go’), the concert series *Aitzealdenk* (‘Do you hear it?’), the video game contest *Klikazank* (‘Click it’), the book *Egañazpi, ezink esan polita ez dela...* (‘Egañazpi, don’t tell me it’s not nice...’), and the slogan of the festival *Gattunk* (‘We are’).

This new form has its limitations, though. Not only because of its lack of tradition, but for morphological reasons as well, since the whole paradigm should be affected. Besides, some combinations may not sound quite right and the minority status of Basque would also be an obstacle when it comes to spreading the new form. Consequently, this new formula may be an asset for slogans and so on, but it seems complicated to extend its use beyond such boundaries. The participants (MAN-69, WOMAN-43) in one of our focus group discussions actually share a similar viewpoint:

Excerpt 1:

MAN-69: Zakilixut made that up.

RESEARCHER: *-nk*.

(...)

MAN-69: That was, that contribution, that was his best contribution. *Aizank*. [“Hey you,” combined unisex form]

WOMAN-43: Yes.

RESEARCHER: There are people against that. Now, is that useful in practice?

MAN-69: It is possible in written texts, but...

WOMAN-43: It’s possible in written texts and besides in short texts. Because, well, if I have to read a novel like that, I get sick, I mean... I would get tired.

However, contrary to what the last participant says, there have been a few attempts to employ this *-nk* form in longer texts. For instance, Lucia Baskaran published the short story ‘Jolas bat baino ez dunk’ (‘It is nothing but a game’) in 2021, in which she uses these innovative epicene forms in all the conversations in which the use of *hika* is deemed appropriate. Another recent example is the well-known graphic novel *Maus* by Art Spiegelman, which was translated into Basque by Julen Gabiria in 2022. An African American character shows up for a couple of strips speaking some sort of vernacular variety of English. The translator deploys a strong accent in the central dialect of Basque, and he also includes the *-nk* forms, probably in order to add further informality to the character’s speech.

Apart from the three strategies suggested by Barquín (2008), other strategies can also be found. On the one hand, those *hika* forms that are epicene by nature can be used, like that

in the title of the local magazine *Noaua* ('Where are you going to'), which covers the current affairs in the Basque town of Usurbil, where *hika* is widely used and the expression 'noaua' written in vernacular is known by everyone. On the other, the mere repetition of both masculine and feminine forms is also in use, as in the song *Ingo yeu, ingo* italicized ('We'll do it, we'll do it') by the well-known musical duo Alaitz and Mainer, written in 2006 for an important festival held in their own hometown, Oiartzun. As a matter of fact, they used the name of the song for an *hika* course⁵ that was organized in 2023 in this same town. Finally, we have to bear in mind that, while gender is encoded in most verbal forms when we use *hika*, Basque pronouns themselves are gender-neutral, and the verb can be elided depending on the context. This is the case in the video-clip contest *Hi eta hire munduak* ('You and your worlds') organized by the magazine aimed at youngsters and kids *Gaztezulo*, the program to promote the Basque language among teenagers *Hire esku* ('In your hands'), *Hi gazte* ('Hey kid'), a public-funded initiative for young artists to create and disseminate cultural products in Basque, and *Hirekin* ('With you'), a technological project promoted by Mondragon University.

Inappropriate use of *hika* from a gender perspective

There are efforts to make *hika* more gender-fair, but if we look at the actual use, a wide range of inappropriate uses of the informal address form have been identified by various researchers. We give an account of these in the following section. The key factor often is not the nature of the language itself, but the use its speakers make of it. In our particular case, the use of *hika* can bring about other sexist issues that are more and more common: using *hika* with boys but *zuka* with girls in a similar context, using male forms as if they were neutral, addressing a mixed group of people using male forms, and even addressing a single female interlocutor with male forms, which seems to be a relatively new trend (Azkue, 2000), but has been perceived as well in other research (Ozaita, 2014).

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The participants in our study have experienced similar situations firsthand. Below, we cite some of them. The following excerpt displays a conversation between two women aged 21 and 74, respectively. The young woman explains to the elderly woman that nowadays most girls address each other in the formal *zuka* whereas most boys use *hika* with other boys, but *zuka* with girls:

Excerpt 2:

WOMAN-21: No. We always use *zuka*, also with my friends. At least when we were kids.

WOMAN-74: It seems that here boys always use *hika*, the young people, but girls use *zuka*.

WOMAN-21: Yes.

WOMAN-74: Yeees. In Azpeitia boys completely in *hika* and girls completely in *zuka*.

WOMAN-21: Yes, it's like that. Boys also address girls in *zuka*.

⁵ Specific courses are offered sporadically to learn how to use the informal address form *hika*. They are typically offered by Basque language schools for adults known as *euskaltegiak*.

Excerpt 3 shows the experience and the feelings of one woman (WOMAN-43) in a given situation. In a meeting attended by both women and men, the male speaker made use of masculine *toka* forms and the participant reported to us that she felt excluded.

Excerpt 3:

WOMAN-43: I was at a meeting recently, both men and women, and he [the speaker] was “well, then we have to do...” [with male forms]. I said, finally I got uncomfortable, like that for two hours... And I felt as if I wasn't there. And I counted us, 19 women and 18 men, more or less. And I said to the guy next to me, “I, I'm leaving, I somehow don't feel included.” (...) No, I mean, let's use *zuka* in plural, like it should be, when there are many people. Because it's true it can become discriminatory in those contexts, right?

In Excerpt 4, a female participant (WOMAN-39) recounts how they, she and her woman friends, used to react when boys addressed them at school using *toka*, i.e., male forms of *hika*.

Excerpt 4:

WOMAN-39: I'm not sure, but it must've been in 7th or 8th grade, something like that. And we also played that game, you know? Boys always spoke to us using male forms, and so we started to talk to them in female forms. A bit like that, you know? In order to... “Hey, what's the matter with you?” [female *hika*]. “Hey, don't you talk to me as if I were a girl...”

MAN-40: Certainly, that bothered them.

WOMAN-39: That did bother them, sure, yeah. And it was then that they started, I think...

MAN-40: Making an effort.

This section has included some telling examples concerning the two recent tendencies. Together with the decline of *hika* in recent decades, an inappropriate use of the informal address form has also become widespread. The first excerpt implicitly also shows that there is a generation gap in the use of *hika*. Some habits and patterns that were inconceivable not long ago have become extremely common within barely two generations. It is logical to suggest that these two tendencies are interrelated. There is a decline in the use of *hika*—resulting from the lack of transmission and models—and an improper use of *hika* regarding the gender of the interlocutor. We have seen how these inappropriate uses may create somewhat uncomfortable situations among women. Some participants told us about feeling ruled out, powerless, or unable to react; others shared stories of standing up for themselves and taking a stance, but the situation may make them feel uneasy in any event.

The conundrum of *hika* and gender binary

This section studies another controversial issue associated with the use of *hika* that may create discomfort among some speakers who identify as non-binary. Beyond the non-sexist use or inclusive use of *hika*, of late some people have called into question the binary system of the informal address form itself while considering gender-neutral *zuka* already

serves as the default address form for most Basque speakers. Gender diversity is a reality in our current society, and most *hika* forms can only address women or men.

Ozaita (2014) explored two opposite viewpoints among the participants in his study. Some thought that gender division does not harm anybody and that *hika* implies linguistic richness within the Basque language. Others thought that *hika* may not work within the current context of gender diversity. Alberdi-Zumeta (2019) also presents contrasting views. In her study, some participants regarded *hika* as backward and sexist due to its binary division, adding that appeal to tradition cannot justify the exclusion. Legorburu (2018) reflects on the dilemma posed by the dichotomy of *hika* against gender diversity, but she is of the opinion that, from a feminist perspective, promoting *hika* –and especially recovering *noka*– can do more good than harm.

When the participants in our study were asked about this issue, the first finding to be highlighted is that their majority had not even thought about it. Nonetheless, among those participants who did share their opinion, they did not see this aspect as problematic:

Excerpt 5:

MAN-30: It's problematic only if we consider it problematic. Once we see that as problematic there's another tool, right? There's the *zuka* tool.

The viewpoint expressed by Legorburu (2018) was supported by was supported by a 43-year-old female participant who perceived that using *hika* has only positive aspects:

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Excerpt 6:

WOMAN-43: "I'm capable of speaking Basque without distinguishing anybody [she is referring to using *zuka*]. When I want to distinguish, it's in an atmosphere in which it's accepted, right? Because both parties have accepted it and besides, I get closer to them. Is there anything more beautiful? That's how I experience it."

Based on the few studies and voices that have addressed this issue, it appears that the potential conflicts that *hika* may encounter in situations involving people of non-binary gender identity are not judged as a problem. Instead, it can be argued that, rather than a drawback, *hika* may have the potential to become a favorable asset regarding sexual diversity. For instance, from a transgender perspective, the theater play *Lur*, which was performed in 2018 for the first time, poses a relevant example: the main character is a trans kid whose grandfather addresses them using female *noka* forms, on account of their sex assigned at birth; however, the kid constructs their own gender identity as the play goes on, and in the end the old man switches to male *toka* forms to address his grandson, leading the audience to believe that he has accepted the kid's gender.

Noka, a tool for women's empowerment

This last section deals with a related question of non-discrimination. It is concerned with the recent change that *noka*, the traditionally female variety of *hika* has been regarded as

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a tool for women’s empowerment of late. In order to understand the current situation of *hika* in general, and female *noka* in particular, we should establish the conventions. As is common in areas where minority languages are spoken, Basque has been considered less prestigious than the majority languages, such as Spanish or French; a similar devaluation applies within the Basque language itself. *Hika* has had a lower status in contrast with the more formal *zuka*; and, within the informal address form, *noka* has had a lower status than its masculine counterpart, *toka*. This idea can be explained by making reference to the work of Irvine and Gal (2000).

Irvine and Gal (2000) describe three semiotic processes by which people construct ideological representations of linguistic differences: iconization, fractal recursivity, and erasure. The case of *hika* we consider an instance of what they call fractal recursivity:

[fractal recursivity] involves the projection of an opposition, salient at some level of relationship, onto some other level. [...] the dichotomizing and partitioning process that was involved in some understood opposition (between groups or linguistic varieties, for example) recurs at other levels. (Irvine and Gal, 2000: 38)

Thus, *hika* has been attributed a bad reputation by alleging that it was the language of “gypsy” people, farmers, and the like, because it was associated with a harsh and rude way of living (Alberdi, 1993). More recent studies have identified similar epithets associated with *hika*: country bumpkin, brutish, forceful, ugly, wild, uneducated, witch-language, ancient, and so on (Alberdi-Zumeta, 2019; Beitia, 2017; Echeverria, 2001, 2020; Legorburu, 2018; Ozaita, 2014). According to Echeverria (2020: 15), nevertheless, “these associations were more acceptable for males than females. Using *noka* (to a female addressee) was seen as particularly disrespectful”.

Nonetheless, in spite of the derogatory consequences of this iconization, we have observed some signs that make us suspect that some sort of a change is taking place. Legorburu (2018) talks about the new paradigm of *hika*, looking at two different trends. On the one hand, the participants in her study attribute other values to *hika*, associating it with “authentic” Basque speakerhood as a key element that indexes group membership. On the other, she suggests that *hika* can serve as a valuable tool to empower women. Women who start to communicate in *noka* become active speakers and assume the agency that women have often been excluded from.

In the same vein, some participants in our study endorse the perceptions pointed out by Legorburu (2018). The following excerpt shows how using *noka* among women can generate a feeling of sorority among them.

Excerpt 7:

WOMAN-43: I don’t know how you guys experience that, probably what you said: closeness. But with other women I experience that as some sort of sisterhood. Then it seems a tool for empowerment to me. And a space for us (...), it’s a space that we feel we still need. If we use *hika* in this space, that is like getting naked and then we can talk openly. It’s similar with men, it’s true that when I use *hika* with a man of my age or similar, I mean, it gets easier, I don’t know how to

explain it. I know I can hold his back at ease, when I address him in *hika* it's like holding his back.
Epa hi! ["Hey you," in *hika*]

What is more, some female participants state that they feel more self-confident when they are speaking in *noka*:

Excerpt 8:

WOMAN-36: Yes, I'd say assurance.

WOMAN-29: Me too, as if I spoke with more...

WOMAN-36: Yeah, that's it, with more power.

WOMAN-29: More confidently.

Beyond individual perceptions, one can argue that this change is more general in society if we take into consideration the various initiatives that have taken place recently. We have witnessed efforts to revitalize *hika* forms, many of them with a clear focus on female forms. An increasing number of women, many of them members of the feminist movement, have started to promote the use of *hika*, especially its female forms, by organizing courses for learning how to use it, by creating practice groups, and also by discussing both the possibilities and risks of these forms⁶.

Within this gradual evolution of *noka*, another indicator may be the increasing use of the once excluded and disregarded forms for branding purposes. More and more examples can be found in the physical and the virtual linguistic landscape. In contrast to male *toka* forms that are used as if they were gender-neutral, *noka* forms are mostly being used for associations and projects run by and aimed at women. Several examples are described briefly below.

Noka is the name of a contemporary band of rock music, formed by three Basque American women singing mostly songs in which *noka* forms are prevalent. *Noka* is also the name of a cultural initiative run in 2021 for the first time by the Basque Government to support female film directors. This tendency is not a completely new phenomenon. The feminist association *Egizan* ('Do it' in the *noka* form) was founded back in 1987, inspiring using *noka* forms as a branding resource. Founded in 2014, the federation *Gu gaitun* ('We are') includes different associations working with prostitutes in the Basque Autonomous Community. *Dinagu* ('We have', loosely translated) is a group of female artists and craftswomen from various fields, and in 2021 they started organizing the itinerant market *Nomadak gaitun!* ('We are nomads!'). The association *Gaitun* released the documentary *Itsasoan gaitun* ('We are in the sea') in 2021, which deals with women who work or have worked in jobs related to the sea. Finally, the podcast *Kirolari gaitun* ('We are sportswomen') on the radio station Naiz Irratia was established in 2021 with the aim of drawing attention to sportswomen and minority sports. These examples of branding may be associated with an increasing visibility and a possible transformation in the traditional meaning(s) of *noka*, resulting in the progressive potential of the Basque informal address form among women in order to empower them.

⁶ https://www.naiz.eus/eu/hemeroteca/gara/editions/2024-02-10/hemeroteca_articles/hitanoa-ez-dago-osasuntsu-baina-bada-biziberritzeko-mugimendua

Conclusion

This paper has explored the case of the informal personal pronoun, *hi*, and its derivative form of address, *hika* in Basque, an isolate language. As we explained, either feminine or masculine gender of the addressee is encoded in most uses of *hika* forms, even when the addressee is not positioned as an argument of the verb. This feature has been categorized as ‘allocutivity’, and it seems to be very rare, which makes its research of special interest.

We discussed four interrelated issues concerning *hika* and gender. They have to do either with the intrinsic nature of the informal address form or with the changing settings of social use of the term. Among the characteristics that are inherent to the grammar of *hika*, it is mostly its gender binary that is questioned recently. If we look at the languages that coexist with Basque (mainly Spanish and French), efforts are being made to avoid gender markers, by using different strategies. The strategies range from duplicating feminine and masculine forms to creating gender-neutral forms. They have had different degrees of acceptance in their respective societies, but the overall tendency seems to be diminishing gender differentiation, avoiding masculine forms for everyone. The obvious question thus arises: Does the promotion of *hika* go in the opposite direction? The answer may be affirmative while it may also be robustly justified.

Nevertheless, the most intriguing finding in our study is that promoting *hika* does not necessarily hinder the path toward a more inclusive approach of language. To meet the requirement of language use that should become more gender-fair and be adapted to the needs of gender non-binary speakers. A gender binary view of language is not suitable for everyone. Yet, there are multiple ways to use *hika* without evoking gender markers. Most of them, though, are restricted to branding purposes, idioms, and so on in our data. This is the case of the pronoun with no verbs, the exclusive use of epicene verb forms, and even the mixed morpheme *-nk* to be attached to the verbs. What is more, for those who are not comfortable with the division set up by the Basque informal address form, formal—and gender-neutral—*zuka* is always available.

These reflections may read as contradictory where there is none. In fact, if we look at the actual pragmatic value of *hika* among the bulk of Basque speakers, we can assume that for most of them anything related to different address forms may be of little importance. According to the last sociolinguistic survey carried out in the whole Basque-speaking area (Basque Government et al., 2024), there are slightly more than 800,000 Basque speakers over 16 years of age. Although the survey does not include anything related to *hika*, it is very well known that most regular Basque speakers only use the formal *zuka* for basically all contexts, and many of them are not even familiar with *hika*. What is more, the profile of Basque speakers has changed because half of all young speakers have acquired the language at school and *hika* forms are only superficially taught—if at all—in academic settings (Bereziartua & Muguruza, 2024).

However, as our study reinforces, among those who are competent in *hika* forms and do use it on a daily basis, it is mostly men talking to other men using masculine *toka* forms. Therefore, quantitatively speaking, gender in relation to the informal address form is not

a major concern. However, among those who care about its use, most appear to see *hika* as an opportunity rather than as a problem.

Gustaffson et al. (2015) examine the attitudes toward the Swedish gender-fair pronoun *hen*, and they highlight the fact that time is a factor of paramount importance and that attitudes may change considerably in a short period of time. It is not realistic to foresee a short-term scenario in which most Basque speakers integrate *hika* into their language repertoire. Even though we are witnessing some attempts of revitalization, the use of the informal address form has decreased considerably in recent decades. The decrease may be due to the fact that *hika* has enjoyed little prestige, and this discrimination has been more noticeable among women and female *noka* forms. This may have led to a lack of transmission of the informal address form, *hika*, in general, and that of the female forms of *noka*, in particular. This could also explain the lack of *hika* speakers, especially of those who would also be using *noka* forms. The inappropriate use of *hika* we noted may be considered a direct consequence of this vulnerable situation.

We have found that the use of *hika* does not need to be problematic for non-binary people, while we identified various situations in which cis women experience weird or even disagreeable moments when they are addressed—directly or indirectly—by masculine *toka* forms. At least three different ideas should be considered in order to avoid such discriminatory circumstances: (1) to raise awareness so that people realize this discrimination exists; (2) to empower women in order to face up to these situations; and (3) to offer specific training and create models so that *hika* speakers learn how and when to use female *noka* forms.

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Sczesny et al. (2016) classify language types regarding expression of gender and gender asymmetries. They argue that with genderless languages, such as Basque, gender-fair language policies are “generally deemed unnecessary” (p. 3). Based on what we discussed in this study, top-down policies may not be needed mostly because they could be regarded as irrelevant by most Basque speakers considering the limited number of *hika* speakers. Nonetheless, if we pursue promoting the informal address form, an *hika* that will be suitable beyond a gender binary distinction for everyone, we highlighted different factors that need to be taken into account.

We have explained some contemporary issues in regard to the relationship between gender and Basque address forms. This study presents different alternatives for the various situations that can take place when speakers use *hika*, as well as a list of real examples that illustrate how *hika* and gender-fair language are not incompatible. *Hika* speakers react in different ways to the sexist use of *hika*, or to what they perceive as such. Nonetheless, our participants do not consider the gender binary nature of *hika* itself as an obstacle. Instead, we are witnessing an effort to revitalize *hika* forms with a focus on feminine *noka* forms, which are being resignified as a tool to empower and create strong bonds among women. More and more young women to whom *hika* has not been transmitted have started learning and using it, while reversing its traditional negative connotations. It is uncertain to what extent this trend will spread in the near future, but today it can be regarded as an opportunity to get closer to the calm after the storm... in a teacup.

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